

1 Water relations, short-chain oligosaccharides and rheological properties in lettuces
2 subjected to limited water supply and low temperature stress

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22 ABSTRACT

23 Reducing water consumption and increasing the quality of vegetables is a particularly
24 high priority in agricultural production. Thus, we set out to analyze the effect of
25 restricting the water supply on water relations, rheological properties, and the
26 accumulation of solutes and protective fructooligosaccharides (FOS) and raffinose
27 family compounds (RFOs) in lettuces grown under controlled greenhouse conditions. In
28 addition, we analyzed whether water restriction can prevent senescence-related changes
29 and overcome the stress imposed by subsequent exposure to low temperature exposure.
30 Lettuces var. Maravilla de Verano were grown under three different water supply
31 regimes, well-watered (WW), moderate water deficit (MWD) and severe water deficit
32 (SWD). Our results indicate that accumulated transpiration (AT) was higher in WW
33 plants than in lettuces subjected to water deficit. The relative water content (RWC) was
34 significantly influenced by a restricted water supply but not by additional low
35 temperature stress. Water deficit caused a significant decrease in the amount of
36 unfreezable water (U_w), determined calorimetrically, in association with a significant
37 decrease in total water content (T_w). After the additional low temperature stress, there
38 was no further drop in T_w , although a significant decrease in U_w was evident, mainly in
39 SWD lettuces. A moderate water deficit enhanced nystose and kestopentaose
40 accumulation. After imposing low temperature stress, MWD lettuces had a lower
41 apparent viscosity, concomitant with an increase in firmness, fewer senescence-related
42 changes and a sharp increase in raffinose. We conclude that moderate water limitation,
43 improving the endogenous levels of FOS and reducing the cleavage of wall
44 polysaccharides backbones, thus reducing viscosity and increasing firmness, could be
45 useful to retain water inside cells, avoiding quality loss and increasing the capacity of
46 the lettuce to resist low non-freezing temperatures.

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48 Key words: water deficit, cold stress, viscosity, water status, fructooligosaccharides,
49 raffinose.

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52 **1. Introduction**

53 Water is a limited natural resource and consequently, there is increased pressure to
54 optimize the efficiency of crop water use. Therefore, reduce water consumption in
55 lettuces during growing is a challenge of special relevance (Gallardo et al., 1996;
56 Tsabedze and Wahome, 2010). Apart from the implication of water supply on processes
57 related to growth, productivity and biomass water plays a relevant role on the quality of
58 horticultural crops (Jones and Tardieu, 1998) mainly in the case of lettuce, with 95% of
59 water (Kim et al., 2016). Indeed, irrigation deficit preserved postharvest quality and
60 shelf-life of fresh cut lettuces (Luna et al., 2012; Vickers et al., 2015). Thus, better
61 insight into the impact of deficient irrigation on the water relations in growing lettuces
62 in terms of water status, osmoprotection and rheological properties is needed.
63 Furthermore, the fact that cold hardiness of a plant seems to be related to its ability to
64 modify the amount and physical state of water (Yoshida et al., 1997) has prompted us to
65 analyze the combined effects of a limited water supply and low temperature stress on
66 water status in growing lettuces. So, an accurate measurement of water status is
67 essential, and a considerable work has been done in this direction (Vertucci and
68 Stushnoff, 1992; Wolfe et al., 2002; Romero and Botía, 2006; Singh et al., 2006; Barg
69 et al., 2009). Indeed, we previously determined water status of fruit tissues and the
70 properties of oligomers relating to water in terms of thermal analysis by differential
71 scanning calorimetry (Goñi et al., 2011; Blanch et al., 2012). We reported that the

72 content of unfreezable water, sometimes called “bound”, meaning the amount of water
73 in a system which does not freeze out as ice at subfreezing temperatures, decreased in
74 fruit tissues during postharvest storage at severe low temperature. However, further
75 work is needed to determine the relationships among water status, accumulation of
76 hydrophilic compounds such as carbohydrates and structural changes in growing
77 lettuces in response to limited water supply and low temperature stress.

78 Various molecular networks, signal pathways and biochemical processes are involved in
79 drought and cold stress (Shinozaki and Yamaguchi-Shinozaki, 2000; Mahajan and
80 Tuteja, 2005; Khan et al., 2016), some of which are involved with the accumulation of
81 osmolytes. Osmoregulation is an important mechanism in plants to decrease the osmotic
82 potential of their tissues through the active accumulation of organic ions or solutes,
83 thereby maintaining a favorable water flow gradient from the soil into the roots under
84 conditions of water deficit. Carbohydrates play important roles in osmoregulation, and
85 FOS and raffinose-oligosaccharides (RFOs) have been associated with plant protection
86 against several stresses, including water deficit (Pilon-Smits, 1999; Livingston et al.,
87 2009, Oliveira et al., 2013; ElSayed et al., 2014; Sengupta et al., 2015). Moreover, these
88 carbohydrates are functional food ingredients (Mussatto and Mancilha, 2007) and short-
89 chain FOS with a low degree of polymerization (DP) have a higher water binding
90 capacity in comparison with other sugars (Furuki, 2002, Blanch et al., 2012). However,
91 FOS compounds are complex mixtures of isomers with different bonds between the
92 monomeric sugar units and with different degree of polymerization that make difficult
93 their characterization and quantification accurately. In the present work we have
94 employed mass spectrometry (MS) to identify and analyze the accumulation of raffinose
95 and short-chain FOS (DP3, DP4 and DP5) in lettuces. Furthermore, the relationship
96 between stress protection and changes in the concentrations of low DP oligosaccharides

97 or of specific isomers remains unclear. It was found that only 1-kestose significantly
98 accumulated in response to low temperature in two cultivars of timothy, while
99 neokestose, 6-kestose, nystose and raffinose did not accumulate in response to low
100 temperature treatments in neither cultivar (Thorsteinsson et al., 2002). 1-Kestose, 6-
101 kestose and 6G-kestose are the templates for further elongation that give rise to inulins,
102 levans and neo-series fructans, respectively. We previously reported increased levels of
103 inulin fructans (DP<6) in strawberries and table grape fruit subjected to beneficial high
104 CO₂ treatment that prevents the structural changes induced by storage at suboptimal low
105 temperatures, while neo-series were not involved (Blanch et al., 2011, 2012). With
106 respect to RFOs, galactinol is the galactosyl-donor exclusive to raffinose synthesis and
107 it increased in association with cold tolerance (Davik et al., 2013). However, no data are
108 available on the behavior of galactinol, and raffinose in lettuce at different levels of
109 water stress with or without further low temperature stress. Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.)
110 is one of the most popular cultivated vegetables in Spain, and the cultivar Maravilla de
111 Verano belonging to the variety *capitata* is cultivated extensively in greenhouses. This
112 lettuce is well appreciated and commercialized for consumption in salads, its crispness
113 being one of the most desired sensory characteristics. Thus, textural and rheological
114 properties of this variety acquire special relevance to determine its deterioration during
115 growing. Furthermore, nutritional value of lettuces can be enhanced by manipulating
116 growing conditions (Baslam and Goicoechea, 2012; Baslam et al., 2013), but the effect
117 of water reduction supply on FOS, oligomers with benefits for plants and humans
118 (Ritsema and Smeekens, 2003), is still unknown.

119 Accordingly, the aims of this work were: 1) to analyze the impact of water deficit, as
120 well as the combination of water deficit and low temperature stress, on water relations
121 and how this relates to the rheological properties and accumulation of organic

122 osmolytes, including FOS, raffinose and galactinol 2) to analyze whether the responses
123 triggered by water deficit are enhanced or diminished when growing lettuces were
124 subjected to additional low temperature stress. With respect to water relations we
125 assessed the accumulated transpiration, relative water content (RWC), unfreezable and
126 freezable water (Uw and Fw) content. The FOS with different DPs, and raffinose and
127 galactinol, were characterized and quantified in lettuce by mass spectrometry.
128 Rheological properties, chromatic characteristics and changes in chlorophylls and
129 carotenoids in Maravilla de Verano lettuces were also determined.

130

131 **2. Materials and Methods**

132 *2.1. Plant material*

133 Seeds of Maravilla de verano (*Lactuca sativa* L. var. *capitata*) were sown in Petri dishes
134 and maintained under conditions of darkness for 8 days. The seedlings were then
135 planted in 1 L plastic pots (40 cm top diameter, 15 cm of bottom diameter and 20 cm
136 high), containing a mixture of peat/perlite (blond peat 50%, black peat 50% and perlite
137 5%). Three days after sowing (DAS), the pots were restricted to only one lettuce plant,
138 that which exhibited the best physical appearance. Plants were watered every two days
139 until the 17th DAS when the imposition of water deficit experiments started. As such,
140 the same amount of water was given to each pot (0.5 L per pot) and after 45 min, when
141 all the water had percolated, this process was repeated twice. Lettuces were grown in a
142 greenhouse at 20 °C day/night temperature and 60–85% relative humidity, and received
143 natural day light supplemented with irradiation from fluorescent lamps (Philips Master
144 TL-D 58W, Holland) that provided a 12060 lux luminous flux during a 16 h
145 photoperiod. To minimize the effects of intra-chamber environmental gradients, the pots
146 were repositioned randomly on the benches every watering day. Water deficit was

147 imposed by ceasing irrigation in two lots of twelve plants each. Three different
148 conditions were imposed: the controls were kept as well-watered (WW) and they were
149 watered to field capacity, according to the water loss by plant transpiration (determined
150 gravimetrically) until the end of experiment; for moderate water deficits (MWD), the
151 pots were not watered for 9 days to achieve 69-70% of the initial pot weight; severe
152 water deficit (SWD) was established by not watering the pots for 16 days, reaching 64-
153 65% of the initial pot weight. The additional low temperature stress was imposed in six
154 pots for each water supply condition by storage in a cold chamber for 7 days at 0 °C ±
155 0.5 °C. Each pot was put in individual 20 L capacity cabinets that permit a relative
156 humidity of 95-98% to be reached and they were not watered throughout the low
157 temperature stress experiment. Six plants per treatment were sampled on each day. In
158 total, 6 different treatments were employed: control, WW and WW combined with low
159 temperature (WW+LT); MWD and MWD combined with low temperature
160 (MWD+LT); and SWD and SWD combined with low temperature (SWD +LT). At the
161 end of each individual treatment and after the combined experiment, all the leaves were
162 collected. The measurements of RWC, Uw and texture were performed always on the
163 third leaf sampled from the rosette and for each sampling day and treatment, 18 leaves
164 from 6 different pots were used. The rest of the leaves were divided into two groups, a
165 part of the fresh material was pressed to obtain raw lettuce juice and used to determine
166 viscosity, total soluble solids (TSS) and color. The remaining leaves material was
167 frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C until use.

168

169 2.2. *Water status determination*

170 The total water (Tw), expressed relative to the dry weight, was determined as:

$$171 \text{ Tw (\%)} = 100 [(PF-PS)/PS]$$

172 The relative water content (RWC) was determined by gravimetric methods, according to
173 the equation:

$$174 \text{ RWC (\%)} = 100 [(PF-PS)/(PT-PS)]$$

175 where PF = fresh weight of the sample; PS = dry weight of the sample and PT = turgid
176 weight.

177 Once cut and weighed, the leaf was split and placed for 24 h into a plastic tube with
178 deionized water at 4 °C in a dark chamber. After 24 h, the leaf was weighed again to
179 obtain the turgid weight and the dry weight of the leaf was then obtained after 48 h in an
180 oven at 80 °C.

181 The accumulated transpiration (AT) per pot was calculated by gravimetric analysis. The
182 pot was weighed before and 24 h after irrigation, and again subjected to irrigation,
183 always at the same time, in function of the treatment: drought or control. The sum of
184 these measurements over treatment period allowed the accumulated transpiration to be
185 calculated.

186 The unfreezable (Uw) and freezable (Fw) water content as well as the freezing onset
187 temperature (T_{fonset}) were determined using a DSC822e differential scanning calorimeter
188 (Mettler-Toledo Inc., Columbus, OH, USA) equipped with a liquid nitrogen cooling
189 accessory, and following the method of Goñi et al., (2007). The melting enthalpy of the
190 samples and that of deionized water, together with the Tw, allowed the Fw and Uw
191 content to be determined. The Uw was calculated as:

$$192 \text{ Uw} = \text{Tw} - \text{Fw}$$

193 where

$$194 \text{ Fw} = \Delta H_{\text{sample}} / \Delta H_{\text{pure water}}$$

195 Both the Fw and Uw were expressed relative to the dry mass, and the Tw was
196 determined after the stable weight had been obtained by oven-drying at 80 °C. At least
197 six measurements were made on each sampling day.

198

199 2.3. Color and total soluble solids

200 The total soluble solids (TSS) content was determined in the juice obtained from the
201 lettuce leaves using a digital refractometer (Atago PR-101, Atago, Japan). The juice
202 chromatic characteristics

203 was measured using a Konica Minolta CM-3500d colorimeter and following the CIE
204 (Commission International de l'Eclairage) system. L^* , a^* , b^* values were measured to
205 describe a three-dimensional color space, and they were used to calculate the chroma
206 $(C) = (a^2 + b^2)^{1/2}$. L^* indicates lightness from 0 (completely opaque or black) to 100
207 (completely transparent or white), a positive a^* indicates redness ($-a^*$ is greenness) and
208 a positive b^* value yellowness ($-b^*$ is blueness). At least five measurements were made
209 on each sampling day.

210

211 2.3.1. Extraction and determination of chlorophylls and carotenoids

212 To determine the chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoids (carotenes and
213 xanthophylls) content, the pigments were extracted in an organic solvent (DMSO,
214 dimethylsulfoxide) according to a modified version of the method proposed by Barnes
215 et al., (1992). The absorbance was measured in a spectrophotometer at 4 different
216 wavelengths: 665 and 649 nm, maximum peaks for chlorophyll a and chlorophyll b
217 absorbance, respectively (red region of the visible spectrum); 480 nm, maximum peak
218 absorbance for carotenoids (blue region of the visible spectrum); and 750 nm to assess
219 the turbidity of the extract. The concentration of the pigments was calculated as:

220 Chlorophyll a ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$): 12.47 Abs 665 – 3.62 Abs 649
221 Chlorophyll b ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$): 25.06 Abs 649 – 6.50 Abs 665
222 Carotenes + Xanthophylls ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = [1000 Abs 480 – 1.29 Chl a – 53.78 Chl b] 220^{-1}
223 The compounds analyzed were expressed as mg g^{-1} dry weight and the data represent
224 the means of the three biological replicates, with two different technical measurements
225 for each.

226

227 2.3.2. *Texture*

228 Textural analysis of leaves was performed by using a TA.HDPlus Texture Analyser
229 (Stable Micro Systems Ltd., Godalming, UK) provided with Texture Exponent software
230 (version 6.1.9.0) and equipped with a 50 N load cell. Firmness of the leaf was
231 determined by measuring the cutting force (N) required to cut it using a blade set with
232 guillotine (HDP/BSG). The trigger force was 0.05 N and the test speed was 10 mm s^{-1} .
233 Tests were performed on samples consisting of one leaf, which was placed horizontally
234 on the slotted blade insert and cut across its longitudinal axis at 1.5, 3 and 6 cm of
235 distance starting from the base of insertion of the leaf.

236

237 2.4. *Rheological properties*

238 Viscosity was measured with a dynamic Kinexus Pro Rotational Rheometer (Malvern
239 Instruments Ltd., Worcestershire, UK) with a cone and plate geometry (4° cone angle,
240 40 mm diameter) that works with small sample volumes (3-4 mL). Rheological
241 measurements were taken at a temperature of 25°C , which was maintained by a Peltier
242 Plate cartridge in the lower plate with a temperature resolution of 0.01°C . The steady
243 state shear measurements were obtained for shear rates ranging from 0.01 to 50 s^{-1} , and

244 the Oswald de Waele or power law model (Eq. (1)) was used to describe the effect of
245 the shear rate on the apparent viscosity of the samples:

$$246 \quad \eta_a = K \dot{\gamma}^{n-1} \quad (1)$$

247 where η_a is the apparent viscosity (Pa s), K is the consistency coefficient (Pa sⁿ), γ is the
248 shear rate (s⁻¹) and n is flow behavior index. For the statistical analysis of the flow
249 curves, viscosity at the intermediate shear rates at (0.1, 1 and 10 s⁻¹) was also compared.
250 Triplicate measurements were taken, at least.

251

252 *2.5. Extraction, characterization and quantification of FOS and raffinose*

253 FOS and raffinose were extracted by the method described previously (Blanch et al.,
254 2017). Frozen leaves (3 g) were homogenized in 4 mL of ultra-pure water and the
255 mixture was boiled under reflux in a water bath for 15 min. After cooling, the samples
256 were sonicated for 10 min at 40 °C and the pH of each sample was adjusted to 7.5 with
257 10% NH₄OH. The samples were then centrifuged for 15 min at 14,700 g and the
258 supernatants were filtered through a membrane of 0.45 μm pore size.

259 The compounds were initially identified by quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) mass
260 spectrometry, using an Agilent 1200 series Liquid Chromatography (LC) system, with a
261 quaternary pump G1311A, an integrated degasser G1322A, a thermostated autosampler
262 G1367B and a thermostated column compartment G1316A. This apparatus was coupled
263 to an Agilent 6530 accurate-mass QTOF LC-MS apparatus with ESI-Jet Stream
264 Technology (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). A 5 μL sample was
265 separated at 30 °C on a Thermo Hypercarb column (100 mm x 2.1 mm, 5 μm particle
266 size: Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany), and eluted using a mobile phase
267 made up of a mixture of 5 mM ammonium formate (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent
268 B) that was applied at a flow rate of 0.4 mL min⁻¹. The solvent gradient was adjusted as

269 follows: 0–1 min, 5% B; 1–5 min, 5–10% B; 5–10 min, 10% B; 10–20 min, 10–50% B;
270 20–25 min, 50% B; 25–30 min, 50–0% B; 30–35 min, 0% B.

271 QTOF acquisition was achieved at high resolution (2 GHz) in MS1 acquisition mode
272 (Min Range m/z 100, Max Range m/z 2500). Ionization was achieved by atmospheric
273 pressure electrospray ionization (ESI) with a drying gas flow rate of 12 L min⁻¹ at
274 350 °C, a sheath gas flow of 6.5 L min⁻¹ at 300 °C, a nebulizer at 45 psi, a cap voltage
275 of 4000 V, a nozzle voltage of 0 V, a fragmentor voltage of 200 V and a skimmer
276 voltage of 65 V. The experiments were carried out at negative polarity with reference
277 masses (m/z) of 119.0363 and 966.0007 to maximize sensitivity. A constant collision
278 energy of 30 eV was employed for auto MS² experiments using the Data Acquisition
279 (version B.04.01) and Qualitative Analysis (version B.04.00) of the MassHunter
280 Workstation software (Agilent Technologies). Samples (5 µL) were injected to analyze
281 the compounds quantified in negative polarity.

282 FOS identification was performed by comparing the retention time of standard 1-
283 kestose and nystose mixtures from Sigma (Steinheim, Germany), and of kestopentaose
284 from Megazyme (Co. Wicklow, Ireland). The compounds analyzed were expressed as
285 µg g⁻¹ fresh weight and the data represent the means of the three biological replicates,
286 with two different technical measurements for each.

287

288 *2.6. Extraction and analysis of galactinol*

289 Galactinol was extracted by the same procedure and it was initially identified by QTOF-
290 MS, as described above. A 2 µL sample was separated on a Tracer Excel C8 120 ODS-
291 B column (25cm x 0.46 cm, 5 µm particle size: Teknokroma, Spain), and eluted with a
292 mobile phase made up of 0.1% formic acid (solvent A) and 0.1% formic acid in
293 acetonitrile (solvent B) at a flow rate of 0.4 mL min⁻¹. The solvent gradient was adjusted

294 as follows: 0–5 min 0% B; 5–22 min 0–50% B; 22–25 min 50% B; 25–28 min 50–0%
295 B; 28–35 min 0% B.

296 The same QTOF acquisition method was used for these compounds as that described
297 above, injecting 2 μL samples to quantify the compounds in negative polarity. The peak
298 with m/z 341 was selected in the ion chromatogram that corresponds to galactinol that
299 was identified with authentic standards. The compound was quantified from the area of
300 its chromatographic peak in EIC mode by comparison with the calibration curves
301 obtained with the galactinol external standard purchased from Sigma (Steinheim,
302 Germany), and expressed in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ fresh weight. Data represent the means of the three
303 biological replicates with two different technical measurements for each.

304

305 *2.7 Statistical analysis*

306 The results are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and the statistical
307 analysis was carried out with SPSS Software version 19.0. One-way analysis of
308 variance (ANOVA) was performed and a multiple comparison of the means were
309 performed with the Tukey's and Duncan's test at a significance level at $P < 0.05$. A
310 principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to investigate the major patterns of
311 correlations among water status measures, solutes, polymers, rheological, color
312 parameters and pigment content. According to Kaiser's criterion, component scores and
313 factor loadings were calculated after variance maximising axis rotation. Only variables
314 with factor loadings > 0.7 were selected for the principal component interpretation.

315

316 **3. Results and Discussion**

317 *3.1. Analysis of the water status*

318 In WW plants, transpiration per pot was twice ($1026.9 \text{ g H}_2\text{O pot}^{-1}$) that of plants
319 subjected to water deficit ($443.1 \text{ g H}_2\text{O pot}^{-1}$; Fig. 1A), and no significant differences in
320 transpiration were observed between MWD and SWD lettuces. The reduction of water
321 loss by transpiration is one of the best characterized responses to water stress. The
322 additional application of low temperature stress (7 days at $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) did not modify the rate
323 of transpiration (Fig. 1A).

324 The highest reduction in RWC (55%; Fig. 1B) was seen in SWD plants. A decrease in
325 RWC values $\geq 30\%$ have been considered indicative of irreversible damage to the
326 photosynthetic machinery (Kaiser, 1987). In MWD plants, the reduction in RWC was
327 only 17% and no reduction in the RWC values evident after the additional low
328 temperature stress. Different stresses may produce an increase, decrease and no change
329 in RWC in plants. Baslam and Goicoechea (2012) reported that leaves of both non-
330 mycorrhizal and mycorrhizal lettuce plants (cv. Maravilla de Verano) maintained
331 control values of RWC when subjected to severe water deficit (a water regime
332 equivalent to $\frac{1}{2}$ of field capacity). Our data show that only severe water deficits cause a
333 marked decrease in the RWC and the combination of water deficit and low temperature
334 stress did not affect RWC. As lettuces were exposed to a saturating atmosphere during 7
335 days of storage at $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, it was no surprise that no differences in RWC were found after
336 low temperature stress.

337 The absolute values (g g^{-1} dry weight) of U_w in lettuce leaves submitted to water deficit
338 and additional low temperature stress was assessed, including the percentage of U_w to
339 T_w (Fig. 1C). WW lettuces had the highest U_w ($4.02 \pm 0.7 \text{ g g}^{-1}$ dry weight) and there
340 was a significant depletion in the U_w in MWD (44.5%, $2.23 \pm 0.4 \text{ g g}^{-1}$ dry weight) and
341 in SWD lettuces (63.1%, $1.48 \pm 0.3 \text{ g g}^{-1}$ dry weight) with respect to the WW lettuces.
342 Despite the differences in the absolute levels of U_w among the three treatments, the

343 percentage of U_w with respect to the T_w was similar (Fig. 1C). These data indicate that
344 the fraction of unfreezable and freezable water and the total water decreased in the same
345 proportion in lettuces subjected to the different levels of water deficit. After low
346 temperature stress, the modification of water status was associated with a significant
347 decrease in the U_w , the highest decrease being evident in SWD lettuces. As T_w did not
348 change, the decrease in unfreezable water caused by the additional low temperature
349 stress seemed to be the result of its conversion to freezable water. Such a conversion
350 might control the swelling of the lettuce's cells in response to low temperature,
351 including the guard cells, thereby avoiding water loss. In sensitive magnetic resonance
352 imaging experiments, cold storage was associated with the conversion of bound water to
353 free water (Bendel et al., 2001). Our data could indicate that the changes in water status
354 provoked by water deficit and low temperature stress could be attributed to a metabolic
355 response in lettuces that modifies mainly the content of hydrophilic components that
356 can interact strongly with water molecules.

357

358 3.2. *Accumulation of solutes*

359 The TSS and T_{fonset} were assessed in lettuces subjected to water deficit and low
360 temperature stress (Fig. 2). TSS was 2.1 times greater in SWD lettuces and 1.1 times
361 higher in MWD lettuces than in control WW lettuces. As expected, the increase in TSS
362 was strongly correlated with the decrease in the T_{fonset} determined calorimetrically,
363 which was lowest in the SWD plants (-5 °C: Fig. 2B). When lettuces under water
364 deficits were subjected to low temperature stress, the T_{fonset} were not significantly
365 altered (Fig. 2B) although the TSS significantly decreased (Fig. 2A). Although the net
366 accumulation of solutes under water stress has been reported in many crop plants as an
367 important mechanism associated with drought tolerance, the sharp accumulation of

368 solutes in SWD lettuces appear to be link to stress. Essini et al., (2009) suggest that
369 osmotic adjustment should be more associated with symptoms of injury instead of being
370 considered as a drought resistance trait.

371

372 *3.3. Rheological properties*

373 The apparent viscosity versus shear rate curves of juices extracted from lettuces
374 submitted to water deficit and low temperature stress were plotted (Fig. 3). As the
375 viscosity decreased as the shear rate increased, all the samples exhibited non-Newtonian
376 shear-thinning behavior due to rearrangements in the conformation of molecules in the
377 dispersion by shearing. The Oswald de Waele or power law model was used to describe
378 the flow curves (Fig. 3). It is well known that the power law model disregards yield
379 stress (Alvarez and Canet, 2013) and therefore, a model accounting for this property
380 would probably adjust better to the flow behavior of these more viscous juices. The
381 juice of SWD plants showed the highest viscosity, which could in part reflect the higher
382 TSS content of these lettuces (Fig. 2A). Contrary, the lowest values were obtained in
383 MWD lettuces after low temperature stress (Fig. 3).

384 The steady state shear rheological parameters of the leaves with distinct access to water
385 supply and exposed to low temperature indicate that while the K values are slightly
386 lower in MWD plants than in WW plants, the K values increased 7-fold in SWD
387 lettuces (Table 1). The additional low temperature stress also modified K values, but the
388 decrease in K values was only significant in SWD plants. Our results indicate that the
389 leaves of SWD plants exhibited the highest viscosity, while those of MWD plants
390 showed the lowest values after 7 days at 0 °C showed the lowest values. The flow
391 behavior index, n , is based on the deviation of the juice from the Newtonian flow, for
392 which $n = 1$. This parameter was below 1 for all treatments, indicating that the juices

393 were pseudoplastic, shear-thinning liquids (Alvarez and Canet, 2013). While the values
394 of n were not significantly affected by the treatments applied, this parameter did tend to
395 increase with the severity of the treatment pointing to a slight loss of pseudoplasticity.
396 In turn, only the viscosities corresponding to SWD plants were significantly higher (P
397 <0.05) than those obtained for the rest of the plants at lower and higher shear rates (0.1
398 and 10 s^{-1}). However, viscosity at the intermediate shear rate (1 s^{-1}) was the parameter
399 most significantly affected by the treatments applied (Table 1). The $\eta_{a,1}$ only increased
400 markedly under SWD and conversely, it decreased significantly in samples subjected to
401 low temperature stress irrespective of their limited water supply. Note that the lowest
402 $\eta_{a,1}$ values were evident in MWD plants subjected to low temperature exposure. These
403 $\eta_{a,1}$ values were therefore in reasonable agreement with the K values from the power law
404 fits, which might be expected considering that they correspond to the apparent viscosity
405 at a shear rate of 1 s^{-1} . Scission of polysaccharides was monitored as decrease in
406 viscosity, a sensitive test for cleavage of polysaccharide backbones (Manning, 1981;
407 Fry, 1998). Thus, the lower viscosity of MWD lettuces compared with those found in
408 SWD or in WW lettuces may be due to a lower freed polymers in the raw juice as a
409 result of a better integrity of their cell walls and a high degree of interconnectivity
410 between wall polymers. By contrast, the increase in viscosity of SWD lettuces indicates
411 considerable cell wall rheological modifications possibly due to solubilization and
412 depolymerization of wall polysaccharides, so affecting the rheological behavior.

413

414 *3.4. Characterization and analysis of fructooligosaccharides (FOS) in lettuces*

415 The short-chain FOS in lettuces submitted to water deficit and low temperature stress
416 were evaluated (Fig. 4A-C) and of the three species of FOS detected (1-kestose [DP3],
417 nystose [DP4] and kestopentaose [DP5]), the highest levels observed in all plants were

418 those of kestopentaose (Fig. 4C), reaching values of approximately 800 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ fresh
419 weight. The levels of kestopentaose increased significantly in MWD lettuces with
420 respect to WW plants and in the SWD lettuces. Likewise, a significant increase in
421 nystose was observed in MWD plants (600 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ fresh weight: Fig. 4B), which was
422 25% higher than that found in WW plants. In terms of 1-kestose, similar values were
423 observed for all conditions of water deficit. The additional exposure to low temperature
424 caused a marked decrease in the FOS levels quantified in MWD lettuces, with up to a
425 50% loss of nystose, a 30% loss of kestopentaose and a 20% loss of 1-kestose. The low
426 levels of 1-kestose and nystose found in SWD plants did not decrease after seven days at
427 0 °C, and the reduction in kestopentaose was less than 20%.

428 The accumulation of RFOs and FOS plays important roles in the protection of plants
429 against water deficit and temperature stress (Valluru and Van den Ende, 2008;
430 Livingston et al., 2009; Peters et al., 2007). Some protective functions might be related
431 to their ability to interact with water molecules, mainly in the case of kestopentaose
432 (Blanch et al., 2012). Indeed, the induction of kestopentaose and nystose in MWD
433 lettuces above levels quantified in control WW plants could indicate a higher level of
434 protection in MWD lettuces. Interestingly, FOS are also considered as functional food
435 ingredients and they have numerous nutraceutical properties (Mussatto and Mancilha,
436 2007).

437

438 *3.5. Analysis of raffinose and galactinol*

439 Among the lettuces submitted to limited water supply and low temperature, the levels of
440 galactinol decreased markedly in SWD lettuces, to 75% the values found in WW plants
441 (11.9 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ fresh weight), while in MWD lettuces the decrease was less than 10% (Fig.
442 5A). The combination of water deficit and low temperature stress only significantly

443 affected MWD plants, further reducing galactinol levels to 5 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ fresh weight (Fig.
444 5A). By contrast, similar galactinol values were quantified before and after exposure to
445 low temperature stress in WW plants. Several roles have been attributed to galactinol
446 (ElSayed et al., 2014; Sengupta et al., 2015) and it has been reported that galactinol
447 concentration decreased during water deficit stress, except for a transient peak at 70%
448 RWC (Peters et al., 2007). The marked decrease of galactinol concentration in SWD
449 lettuces and in MWD plants after low temperature stress is consistent with a suitable
450 biomarker of environmental stresses associated with osmotic imbalance (Blanch et al.,
451 2017). While water deficit caused a progressive decrease in raffinose (Fig. 5B), low
452 temperature increased significantly the concentration of this sucrose-related
453 trisaccharide in WW and MWD lettuces and, surpassing even the values found in
454 control WW lettuces. The increase in the concentration of raffinose triggered by 7 days
455 at 0 °C was particularly relevant in MWD lettuces (2.5 times), although no such increase
456 was observed in SWD lettuces. Thus, slight limited water supply seems to favor the
457 synthesis of raffinose, which may play a protective role against low temperature stress.
458 By contrast, severe water deficit did not allow to the plant to trigger an appropriate
459 response to overcome low temperature stress, failing to increase the levels of raffinose.
460

461 *3.6 Firmness, chromatic characteristics and pigment content*

462 The firmness results from cut 1 showed that neither the water deficit nor the additional
463 stress caused by low temperature significantly modified the values of firmness (Fig.
464 6A). Nevertheless, significant softening was evident in the leaves subjected to water
465 deficit at cuts 2 and 3 (Fig. 6B and C), which was more severe at cut 3 than cut 2.
466 Although in both cuts the softening appeared to be more intense in SWD plants, it was
467 not significantly different to that in MWD plants. Since cellular turgor is an important

468 component of the rigidity and firmness of plant tissues, it would appear that the severe
469 water deficit possibly caused a decline in turgor and consequently, a loss of cellular
470 integrity that was reflected as a significant decrease of firmness. Nevertheless, the
471 addition of low temperature stress to the water deficit scarcely affected the firmness of
472 the tissues at cuts 1 and 2, and it tended to only mildly increase firmness in MWD and
473 WW plants at cut 2. However, at the furthest point from the basal point (cut 3), the
474 tissue was significantly firmer in MWD plants after exposure to low temperature,
475 reaching values similar to those found in WW lettuces.

476 Since, firmness is related to the consumer's perception of wilting and freshness, it seems
477 that small increases in firmness may be acceptable and even desirable. Thus, exposure
478 to low temperature modified the structure of MWD plants increasing firmness and so
479 improving their quality in term of freshness. Considering that the textural properties of a
480 plant organ are determined by the relative proportion of the different tissues, the highly
481 reduced parenchymal tissue in cut 1 could explain the lack of significant differences in
482 lettuces subjected to water and low temperature stress. The higher relative proportion of
483 thin-walled parenchymal tissue at cut 3 allowed differences between the treatments to
484 be detected. It has been reported that the specific textural characteristics exhibited by
485 parenchymal tissues of plants are due to the size and shape of their cells, the ratio of the
486 cytoplasm to the vacuoles, the volume of intercellular spaces, the thickness of the cell
487 wall, the osmotic pressure and the type of solutes present in the cell (Ilker and
488 Szczesniak, 1990). Indeed, the increase in firmness at cut 3 in MWD lettuce leaves after
489 exposure to low temperatures might be explained by the changes in the physical
490 properties of the cell wall, mainly the lower polymer turnover and a high degree of
491 interconnectivity between wall polymers. Certainly, the lowest viscosity was found in
492 the raw juice of MWD lettuces after 7 days at 0 °C.

493 The chromatic characteristics of WW, MWD and SWD plants subsequently maintained
494 at 0 °C for 7 days were assessed, highlighting the decrease in lightness of SWD plants
495 (reflected by a decrease in L^* : Table 2). Except for the MWD plants, exposure to low
496 temperature stress caused a decrease in the values of parameter L^* and while the most
497 negative values of the parameter a^* were observed in WW plants, this parameter
498 increased as the limitation of water augmented. Irrespective of the water irrigation
499 regime, lettuces submitted to low temperature stress lost some green color and their a^*
500 values became more positive. The appearance of red colors in leaves of some species
501 caused by the accumulation of anthocyanins has been reported as a visual symptom of
502 leaf senescence (Hoch et al., 2003). In Maravilla de Verano lettuces continuous and
503 moderate water limitation apparently has no effect on the accumulation of anthocyanins
504 (Baslam and Goicoechea, 2012). A severe water deficit combined with low temperature
505 stress resulted in the lowest values of parameter b^* and C, these lettuces losing intensity
506 of their green color. Our results indicate that the additional low temperature exposure
507 resulted in an increase in the lightness of MWD lettuces (reflected by an increase in L^*),
508 even above that of WW lettuces. The increase in lightness observed in MWD plants
509 leads us to suggest they have better browning control. The alterations derived from
510 water shortage and low temperature stress in SWD lettuces and the poorer stability of
511 the green color might be associated with oxidative damage, which in turn influences the
512 development of browning.

513 Analyzing the chlorophyll a, b and carotenoids of WW, MWD and SWD plants before
514 and after low temperature exposure indicated that the chlorophyll a was the predominant
515 pigment in all the plants (Table 2). The lowest concentration of chlorophyll a and b and
516 was found in SWD plants (1.86 mg g⁻¹ dry weight of chlorophyll a and 0.7 mg g⁻¹ dry
517 weight of chlorophyll b) and no significant differences were observed between MWD

518 and WW lettuces. These data seem to indicate that lettuces subjected to severe water
519 regime undergo greater senescence than those with a moderate water supply. A decline
520 in chlorophylls with advanced senescence and increases in the ratio of carotenoids to
521 chlorophylls have been reported during drought-induced leaf senescence in several
522 species (Munné-Bosh and Alegre 2004). The lowest values of carotenoids were
523 quantified in SWD lettuces and no significant differences were observed between MWD
524 and WW lettuces. Based on studies reporting carotenoid contents, crisphead lettuce
525 Maravilla de Verano is a valuable source of carotenoids (Baslam and Goicoechea.,
526 2012; Kim et al., 2016).

527

528 *3.7 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)*

529 A PCA was performed on the set of variables in lettuces subjected to different levels of
530 water deficit and other after additional low temperature stress (Fig. 7). In terms of the
531 water deficit, 89.38 % of the explained accumulated variance in the set of variables
532 could be explained by three statistically significant principal components. The first
533 principal component (PC1) explained 61.29% of the total variance. Analyzing the
534 relationship of this component with the initial variables, and taking into account the
535 both the sign and the magnitude of the correlations, PC1 shows the main positive
536 correlation with the T_{fonset} followed by galactinol, and water status variables. On the
537 contrary PC1 has only major negative correlation with color a^* parameter, TSS and
538 viscosity. PC2 was exclusively correlated positively with short-chain FOS irrespective
539 of the rest of the variables and more strongly with FOS with a higher DP. PC3
540 explained only 10.03% of total variance and only with the firmness at cut 1, 1.5 cm
541 from the base of the leaf, mainly formed by the major longitudinal vein of the leaf.
542 These results place the decrease in freezing onset temperature as one of the variables

543 that best explains the water deficit. Also, these results confirm that water deficit brings
544 about a decrease in the water status, a higher viscosity linked to an accumulation of
545 solutes, and redness. After exposure to low temperature stress, the set of variables could
546 be explained by three components that explain 91.88 % of the accumulated variance and
547 galactinol showed again a very high positive correlation with PC1. The PC2 that
548 accounted for 26.43 % of total variance, was correlated negatively with short-chain
549 FOS, especially nystose and kestopentaose, and viscosity, as well as a strong positive
550 correlation with lightness. These results confirm that after exposure to low temperature
551 the decrease in the viscosity linked to changes in the content short-chain FOS (DP 4 and
552 DP5). The third principal component (PC3) that account for 12.56 % of total variance,
553 was again dominated by the firmness at cut 1 followed by carotenoids (factor
554 loadings >0.7)

555

556 **4. Conclusions**

557 The characterization and quantification of short-chain FOS in lettuce revealed that
558 kestopentaose was the main compound followed by nystose, with the highest levels of
559 these FOS quantified in MWD lettuces. The enhancement of kestopentaose and nystose
560 in MWD lettuces could indicate a higher level of protection in these lettuces.
561 Additionally, moderate water deficit seems to favor the synthesis of raffinose after low
562 temperature exposure, which may play a protective role against low temperature stress.
563 By contrast, severe water deficit did not allow to the plant to trigger an appropriate
564 response to overcome low temperature stress, failing to increase the levels of raffinose.
565 Furthermore, the marked decrease in unfreezable water fraction and the increase in
566 viscosity of lettuces subjected to severe water deficit indicate considerable cell wall
567 rheological modifications possibly due to the loss of water from the wall matrix that can

568 result in disruption of polymer organization, so affecting the rheological behavior and
569 texture.

570

571

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575

576 **Legends**

577

578 Figure 1. Effects of varying water regime (WW = well watered; MWD = moderate
579 water deficit; SWD = severe water deficit) and the additional low temperature stress for
580 7 days at 0 °C (LT) on water status of growing Maravilla de Verano lettuces. A)
581 Accumulation transpiration per pot (g). B) Relative water content (RWC, %). C)
582 Unfreezable water (Uw) content (g g^{-1} dry weight), including in the corresponding bars
583 the percentage of Uw with respect to the total water content (Tw). At least six
584 measurements were made on each sampling day.

585

586 Figure 2. Effects of varying water regime (WW = well watered; MWD = moderate
587 water deficit; SWD = severe water deficit) and the additional low temperature stress for
588 7 days at 0 °C (LT) on A) total soluble solids (%) and B) freezing onset temperature
589 (°C) of growing Maravilla de Verano lettuces. Triplicate measurements were taken, at
590 least.

591

592 Figure 3. Apparent viscosities at different shear rates ranging from 0.01 to 50 s⁻¹ for raw
593 juice of Maravilla de Verano lettuces subjected to different watering regime (solid
594 triangle, WW = well watered,; solid square, MWD = moderate water deficit; solid
595 circle, SWD = severe water deficit) and the additional low temperature stress (hollow
596 triangle WW + LT; hollow square MWD + LT; hollow circle SWD + LT). Triplicate
597 measurements were taken, at least.

598

599 Figure 4. Effects of varying water regime (WW = well watered; MWD = moderate
600 water deficit; SWD = severe water deficit) and the additional low temperature stress for
601 7 days at 0 °C (LT) on short-chain FOS content in growing Maravilla de Verano
602 lettuces. A) 1-kestose (DP3); B) nystose (DP4); C) kestopentaose (DP5). The
603 compounds analyzed were expressed as µg g⁻¹ fresh weight and the data represent the
604 means of the three biological replicates, with two different technical measurements for
605 each.

606

607 Figure 5. Effects of varying water regime (WW = well watered; MWD = moderate
608 water deficit; SWD = severe water deficit) and the additional low temperature stress for
609 7 days at 0 °C (LT) on A) galactinol content and B) raffinose content of growing
610 Maravilla de Verano lettuces. The compounds analyzed were expressed as µg g⁻¹ fresh
611 weight and the data represent the means of the three biological replicates, with two
612 different technical measurements for each.

613

614

615 Figure 6. Firmness of the leaf of Maravilla de Verano lettuce determined by measuring
616 the cutting force (N) required to cut across its longitudinal axis at 1.5, 3 and 6 cm of

617 distance, using a blade set with guillotine. Lettuces were subjected to different water
618 deficit (WW = well watered; MWD = moderate water deficit; SWD = severe water
619 deficit) and additional low temperature stress for 7 days at 0 °C (LT).

620

621 Figure 7. PCA performed on the set of variables in lettuces subjected to different levels
622 of water deficit and additional low temperature stress.

623

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